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Now more than ever, the modern workforce sustained change is in reach. Organizations ensure functional diversity, equity, and inclusion. Integrating persons with disabilities among companies to improve the labor force integrates accommodations as a systemic review. The topic of inclusion appears of importance in the workforce. The inclusion of persons with disabilities seems fearful for many leaders, and the management force's implication results in its success for the organization and the employees at all levels. These initiatives in the marketplace are described as a strategic necessity advantage for their growth, developing unusual and exceptional relationships. We present results of the effects of change on the workforce and its Leadership participating in an inclusive team through behaviors and perceptions are the primary focus of the research.

1 INTRODUCTION

Now more than ever, the modern workforce sustained change is in reach. Organizations ensure functional diversity, equity, and inclusion. Integrating persons with disabilities (PWD¹) among companies to improve the labor force is to blend accommodations as a systemic review. Beyond the accommodation, the PWD must be part of the functional link of the organization's human resources. These initiatives in the marketplace are described as a strategic necessity advantage for their growth, developing unusual and exceptional relationships (Henderson, 2008; Vogel, 2012). Randy Lewis, retired SVP of Operations & Logistics for Walgreens, is the champion initiator of PWD inclusion employment; several steps in integrating the strategic business decision would forever change the distribution centers culture at Walgreens. "It gives people with disabilities an opportunity and makes it not about them but the "US" in the workforce (Lewis, 2014)." Beyond strategic success, what about the effect directly on leaders?

The topic of inclusion appears of importance in the workforce. The inclusion of people with disabilities (PWD) seems fearful for many leaders, and the management force's implication results in its success for the organization and the employees at all levels. Studying the effects of change on the workforce and its Leadership is the primary focus of the research.

¹ Persons with Disabilities (PWD): The Americans with Disabilities Act (2020) defines an individual with a disability as a person who has a physical or mental impairment that substantially limits one or more major life activities, a person who has a history or record of such an impairment, or a person who is perceived by others as having such an impairment.

The sector of focus in the business world was initiated by Mr. Randy Lewis, an inspiring figure and champion of disability employment at Walgreens. Another similar sector was inspired by the inclusion of the PWD process and its results on different scales (productivity, absenteeism), demonstrating positive outcomes.

LITERATURE REVIEW

Inclusion of Persons with Disabilities in Workforce

Vast Underrepresented of Persons with Disabilities in Workforce

An average of 12.6 percent of a person with a disability was reported in 2018 in the United States, giving 40,585,700 reported disabilities out of 323,289,900 total population. Of that number of people reported with a disability with ages to work between 21-64 ages, an estimate of 37.8 percent only were employed in 2018 (Disability Statistics, 2018).

In 2020, of the total of the civilian labor force, the number of unemployed persons with a disability was 23,796,000 (U.S. Bureau of Labor Statistics, 2021). The statistics demonstrate that persons with disabilities are less likely to be employed than non-disabled.

A study on the Work Trends accomplish in 2003 by the John J. Heldrich Center for Workforce Development at Rutgers University disclosed results of only 25 percent of the 500 employers interview mentioned having less than one worker with a disability (Henderson, 2008).

Overview on Disability Inclusion

In some organizations, jobs are given to individuals with disabilities; the manager must go past the stereotype that the hiring was an act of charity. We must not confuse; disability inclusion is more than just offering a job in an organization. Therefore, disability inclusion's best representation is for PWD to be part of the team; it fully includes them in the workforce and does not separate them into enclaves (Lewis, 2014). The translation to an inclusive environment in its own right in the organization. The disability inclusion component standpoint of sense of belongingness in the workforce and breaking stigma and developing an appraisal of others in the work environment; the authenticity of the worker's acceptance in the workforce (Santuzzi et al., 2020; Heera & Maini, 2018). Unfortunately, even if we observe an expanding trend in the benefits of organizations offering PWD opportunities in employment, these persons still experience a sense of job insecurity, underemployment, and unemployment (Tomczak, 2021). Many companies struggle with employee retention, presenting disability inclusion as an alternative. Moore et al. (2020) investigate the factors that make employees with disabilities successful. Research indicates that employees with disabilities are just as successful as their counterparts—with a notable distinction. They often exhibit more loyalty and retention than their non-disabled counterparts (Moore; Hankins; Doughty, 2020). The researcher's analysis with the case study approach at Walgreens on leaders was initially defined as autocratic managers and evolved to a more inclusive relations-based leadership in their inclusive management (Moore; Hanson; Maxey, 2020).

Inclusive Management

A company's transformation analysis of a culture to an inclusive workplace. Transformation of an autocratic leadership style to inclusive management and the role of complexity leadership theory. They analyze the data answering the inquiry of different managers' empowerment to integrate and develop employees with disabilities, presenting different models of transition theories to inclusive management, attributes of the inclusive management style, and enabling tension of performance improvement plans (Moore; Maxey; Wait; Wendover, 2020)

Heera et al. (2018) investigate the different influence factors for an inclusive PWD in the workforce. They refer to and describe the leadership theory of Bennis & Nanus (1987) as volatility, uncertainty, complexity, and ambiguity (VUCA). They are presenting diversity and inclusion as an agenda for a leader to apply effective management. Prioritizing an inclusive workforce in its culture can result successful in the VUCA framework. The leader is a critical player between the inclusive management team and employee engagement, demonstrating a systematic review of the literature and categorizing in a diversity intelligence and inclusive leadership model. (Rathore et al. 2021). The different strategies for designing and implementing effective inclusion, underpinning themes such as organizational culture, accommodation, support network, and job fit. (Heera & Maini, 2018).

The management team is facing several adaptations in their executive functioning to improve the job retention of PWDs; for example, providing direct but sensitive feedback, the frequency of meetings depending on individual needs but with regularity and repeatability, modification in communication (Tomczak, 2021; Heera & Maini, 2018).

Perceptions on Hiring Persons with Disabilities

The relationship between supervisors and PWD subordinates and the positive employer's attitude on inclusion in the workforce results in a non-discrimination perception. The employees of such organizations with dedicated human resources in diverse, inclusive teams feel support and acceptance from their managers (Heera & Maini, 2018). The acceptance in the workforce presents different benefits for PWD to be productive citizens by earning their lives and be given a chance with a job they probably never had before. They are changing the perspective of bureaucratic systems, culture, and paradigms to an inclusive workplace, evoking the importance of patience and determination (Henderson, 2008). Employers' responsibility to help with acceptance of PWD in their teams and pave the way to disclose their needs to be successful; highlights substantial benefits and positive perceptions of them like trustworthiness, reliability integrity, attention to detail, work satisfaction, performance, and low absenteeism (Lindsay et al., 2021).

METHODOLOGY

This research aims to examine and elaborate on how people, supervisors, and associates change through participation in an inclusive team; in different distribution centers

employing PWD among the workforce. The privilege opportunity to analyze and study the different distribution centers of an international organization, Sephora, that integrated the inclusion program inspired by the Walgreens formula.

Owned by luxury conglomerate LVMH (Louis Vuitton Moët Hennessy), Sephora has taken similar strategies as Walgreens in some of its distribution centers in the United States to employ PWD. We are surveying Sephora's supervisors and associated with documenting the business impact of the inclusive workplace; about 738 Sephora employees are joining the research by filling out a survey. The different employees have completed the surveys throughout the distributions centers located in the United States. The theory of positive correlation examines the behaviors and perceptions of the supervisors and associates in the inclusive team. Behaviors and perceptions defined the dependent variables. The independent variables were defined by the positive change of supervisors and associates. How are people change participating in an inclusive team in the workforce through their behaviors and perceptions?

The main interest and highlight on exclusionary management practices are how an inclusive company can benefit from the unique context by employing PWD. The research would be inclusive in revolutionizing employment opportunities for PWD as active players in the modern workforce. There are expectations in the business world to be doing well by doing good; we can analyze the impacts of inclusivity on the executive team, management team, staff, community, to name a few. Society can benefit from these people to be productive citizens by earning their lives and be given a chance with a job they probably never had before (Henderson, 2008). Understanding the success of the inclusive organization is essential for future researches (Moore et al., 2020).

Research Approach: Methodology Framework

We are a research team comprised of Anderson University of human resources, management, psychology, and disability champion Mr. Randy Lewis. The research method would be quantitative methods for nonexperimental designs, such as surveys; questionnaires developed to measure the impact of employees with disabilities on their fellow team members and managers. Search questions

The research team developed the four research questions on this focus; these were the hypotheses to test and connected employee productivity numbers (average of 2 weeks of work) to their survey responses to determine productivity rates by group. We will analyze close-ended questions, numeric data, observational data, attitude data with statistical analysis and interpretation (Creswell, 2018). Quantitative research overviews the data collection and analysis to search for facts, the "what" (numeric, statistics). Components of this method include an overview of the study's design, the characteristics of the population and sample, the instrument used in collecting the data (surveys or experimental), and the steps used in analyzing the data (Creswell, 1994).

As Creswell (2018) mentioned, quantitative research questions inquire about relationships among investigated variables; quantitative hypotheses predict expected outcomes of relationships among variables. The quantitative method deduces new knowledge that relies heavily on logical reasoning based on prior insights and

understanding along existing or adjacent paths; numerical data transformed into efficient displays, variance-based theorizing, and data collection and analysis aligned with the research question (Bansal et al., 2018).

Developments in statistics and using analytics tools, ensuring the data is valid and reliable. We need to have enough incidences on the date to count their conjunctions in a meaningful way, representing behavioral and mental facts. Research based on the quantitative method assures us (statistical confidence) to see beyond our subjective experience based on incidences (Barnham, 2017).

Theoretical Framework of Complexity Leadership

Different concepts to explain the trajectory of complexity leadership theory. In *The Principles of Scientific Management (1911)*, Taylor's industrial bureaucracy model emphasizes management as a top-down, more authoritative, labor approach (Taylor, 1972). This model reinforced trained managers' active role leaving the frontline team as a non-active and non-judgemental role, but emphasizing employee empowerment dominates the bureaucratic paradigms—the standardization of Taylor's implementing methods to increase production (Hamel, Zanini, 2020). In the last century, defining this leadership process was adequate for an economy premised on production-oriented.

With the years in organizations, Leadership shifted by giving importance to a more knowledge-oriented economy facing globalization and technology revolution (Uhl-Bien et al., 2007; Northouse, 2019). Over the years, researchers developed a framework for complexity theory, examining different systems sharing behavioral, unpredictable, disorderly, nonlinear, and uncontrollable templates that seem complex, adaptive, and self-organizing (Burns, 2001; Anderson 1999). The complexity leadership theory identifies and explores different strategies and behaviors within a knowledge-producing context, promoting creativity, learning, and adaptability when appropriate complex adaptive systems are in place. Therefore, distinguish Leadership from a managerial position to produce outcomes aligned with its vision and mission (Uhl-Bien et al., 2007).

In the Knowledge-Era, in contrast to the Industrial age, views are explained more organizational complex abandoning individual and controlling views. Complexity concepts seek adaptation by minimizing leader centricity, control, and hierarchal constraints (Hanson, 2020). Even though bureaucratic settings are still grounded in this new Era, this approach tends in a complex setting (Uhl-Bien et al., 2007). Complexity leadership theory is an entanglement relation between formal (top-down) and informal (complex adaptive system). Furthermore, three functions in the complexity leadership for leaders are administrative, adaptive, and enabling (Uhl-Bien et al., 2007; Hanson, 2020):

- Administrative Leadership recommended support towards their employees instead of controlling, loosened formal structures, raised productivity tension, allocates resources to achieve goals.
- Adaptive Leadership resumes adaptive, creative, and learning actions emerging from workers' interactions to propose solutions or plans.
- Enabling Leadership's role is to effectively manage the entanglement processes between administrative and adaptive Leadership to facilitate employees' efforts.

Data Collection

For the analysis to be accurate and the inferences and hypotheses made precisely and representativeness, the larger the sample size is predetermining the research results (Creswell, 2018; Fowler, 2014; Schutt, 2019). Bickman (2014) precise that as a more significant number of units can give a breadth of information to illustrate the results, increases precision, we tend to large sample size for this study, with 738 participants from four distribution centers at Sephora in the United States out of 1,200 employees in total.

Selecting a subset of the workforce for the research is limited to the employees in specific distribution centers. The sampling helps identify the subjects to collect data; it does not include all employees, only the supervisors, and associates. The probability sampling technique that suits this exploratory and descriptive research (Bickman, 2009 & Creswell, 2018) is the stratified method. The stratification method explains that specific characteristics of individuals are represented in the sample, and the population can be divided into strata (groups), for instance, supervisors and associates with or without a disability. We ensure the representation of some characteristics, even if they are present or not in the sample (Creswell, 2018; Bickman, 2019; Fowler, 2014). As Fowler (2014) mentioned, evaluating different aspects is essential to the sample frame, such as comprehensiveness of the population to cover, probability of selection, and efficiency of target members found in the sample frame.

The population that interests us particularly in this research is the workforce in some distribution centers with people with disabilities within their team—the importance of obtaining information from supervisors and associates in the different work teams, employees with disabilities or not. This population will give an accurate picture to generalize the learnings to a more extensive set (Creswell, 2018).

The sampling bias that might affect the study is the difference between the study population value and the expected value for the sample (Bickman, 2019). Bickman (2019) explains that if the probability of selection is not equal, adjustments of the population parameter estimates by using weights to compensate for the unequal selection probabilities to avoid that bias in the sample.

Data Analysis

In the study, we want to analyze the causality between variables. The variables help form theories and hypotheses, and they refer to a characteristic or attribute of an individual or organization to be measured that varies (Creswell, 2018).

This survey study aims to examine and elaborate on how employees, meaning supervisors, and associates, change through participation in an inclusive team; in different distribution centers employing PWD among the workforce. This study's research population is divided into independent variables: systematically manipulating data to analyze the positive change of the associates and the supervisors in the inclusion concept.

The predictors of the study, with the keys variables, determine whether the correlation theory will examine the behaviors and perceptions of the supervisors and associates in the inclusive team. The type of behaviors and perceptions defines the dependent variables or outcomes and whether they positively impact, change, or causality in the workforce.

Operationalizing the variable is a necessary process of defining them into concepts that can be concrete measurable. This step must be evaluated to construct the validity of the data, lighting the causality relationship mentioned in the research hypothesis (Creswell, 2018 & Cherulnik, 2001). Measuring variables with a scoring survey to collect multiple measures relating to behaviors and perceptions; processing may analyze different potential cofounding variables of interest (Creswell, 2018). The importance of quality in measurements is of concern for the precision and degree of error. In order to measure with precision, the researcher's choice in the type of measurement scale is a decisive step; choosing a nominal scale, ordinal scale, interval scale, and ratio scale (Cherulnik, 2001).

FINDINGS

Perspectives of the Workforce on Disabled Employees and their Teams

This research aims to examine and elaborate on how people, supervisors, and associates change by participating in an inclusive team; in different distribution centers employing PWD. The preliminary results of our analysis on the perceptions were to evaluate the effect on employees' moral elevation by working with PWD in their team. We asked questions on this subject using a Likert-type five-point scale (strongly disagree to strongly disagree) with factor analysis asking questions about team members with disabilities to estimate moral elevation and perspectives. The perceptions analyzed of the associates on their co-workers with disabilities were, for example, if they helped them to be a better team member, if they taught them not to be so quick to give up on people, to make them a better person and in other aspects of their lives or that their success is important to them. This research demonstrates significant results regarding the employees' perspective in distributions centers on hiring people with disabilities and their performance on the job.

Impact of Inclusion on Perspectives of Elements of Performance of the Workforce and Moral Elevation

Our findings on the workforce's perception of the company hiring people with disabilities show that it should not cost more to the organization (see Figure 1). The mean differences between the distribution centers are significant; we can point out the SDC and WDC are higher than the others. The distribution centers, SDC and WDC, showing the highest favorable perception aligned with the higher rate of PWD within the workforce. The inclusion initiative of the PDC shows the lowest rate and the fewer PWD employee in this distribution center.

Figure 1: Perception of the company hiring people with disabilities

Our findings on the workforce's perception of the company hiring people with disabilities show that people with disabilities should be held to the same performance standard as non-disabled employees (see Figure 2). The distribution centers, SDC and WDC, showing the highest favorable perception. The means differences results between the distribution centers are significant; we can point out again the SDC and WDC are higher than the others.

Figure 2: Perception of the company hiring people with disabilities should be held to the same performance standard as non-disabled employees.

Figure 3 elaborates the results on the team's members with disabilities' performance on the job. More precisely, questioning on if they have made the team more effective. The results vary from a mean of 3.5 to 4 out of a Likert-type scale of 5. The distribution

center SDC and WDC are significantly higher than the others. The positive effects of team members working with PWD as a team member truly reflect the impacts they portray on others.

Figure 3: Perception of the workforce on team members with disabilities performance on the job has made the team more effective

These findings in Table 1 show how employees with disabilities are more productive (combined in the productivity report: less absenteeism and safety incidents) than over 650 non-disabled counterparts. The high productivity rate in these distribution centers (SDC and WDC) represents the other results presented and explains the significance of PWD employees in the workforce.

Table 1: Sephora employee survey on perceptions of working with PWD combined with productivity reports

	SDC		WDC	
	N	Productivity rate	N	Productivity rate
Typical rate	398	128%	394	116%
PWD rate	15	144%	37	152%

The moral elevation analysis correlates the number of PWD employees on the team and employees' responses to the survey questions regarding this factor (i.e., they helped me be a better team members, they taught me not to be so quick to give up on people, they made me a better person in other aspects of my life, and their success is important to me). Figure 4 shows the more team members with PWD on a team cause the workforce to rate the effects stronger, meaning the employees with PWD leads to better effects. The percentage correlates with questions regrouping this factor analysis of moral elevation with a five-point scale (strongly disagree 1, strongly disagree 5).

Figure 4: Percentage of PWD on team predicting overall moral elevation

DISCUSSION

This study is primary research on the change in the workforce will participate in an inclusive team through their behaviors and perceptions. The results of our research data allow us to see that there is a direct link between the positivism that team members may exhibit when working with team members with a disability. Our results reported a direct link to the presence of people with disabilities on overall morale uplift. Other factors can be researched to see other elements that can show us the direct effect on other corporate sphere organizations, management, direct and indirect costs and human resources. There is much work to concretely demonstrate the practical realities on the whole organization of people with disabilities. After a more exhaustive demonstration on the subject, he will present the different steps at the executive level to strategically modify his business plan and culture to make it a real long-term success.

CONCLUSION

We present results of the effects of change on the workforce and its Leadership participating in an inclusive team through behaviors and perceptions were the primary focus of the research. Now more than ever, the modern workforce sustained change is in reach with the scarcity of labor. We have seen the organizations ensure functional systemic, and strategical aspects by focusing on the inclusion of PWD in the workforce. The inclusion of PWD reviewed at a high level of management strategies guarantees its success should be supported with further researches to explore this avenue at a corporate level. In their strategic development as an advantage for their growth, these initiatives, developing unusual and exceptional relationships is not enough to analyze the actual market value of this change.

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